

THE ANTHROPOLOGICAL SENSE ABOUT WHY STORIES SHOULD BE READ TO CHILDREN BEFORE BED

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ABSTRACT

This essay addresses the theme of the practice of telling stories to children at bedtime, in an attempt to understand the anthropological meaning of why such an act is carried out. Its scientific relevance lies in enabling discussion and in-depth study of an action that emerged in the history of humanity even before humans had mastered articulated speech, being expressed in the form of soft and melodious sounds, which were intended to provide a balanced and peaceful sleep for young children. Its social relevance lies in helping mothers and fathers understand the need to apply this action to their children, considering that it can help in the formation of the egosyntonic, in overcoming the Oedipal phase and also expands the cognitive, creative and intellectual potential, considering the attempt, on the part of the child, to resolve the conflicts generated by the accommodation process. The story told by the mother to the child at bedtime should have no other interest than to make the child sleep peacefully, feeling safe and welcomed. Everything else that goes beyond this must be of the child's particular and autonomous interest, and it is up to him to make the assimilations in the way he sees fit, including seeking help when he deems it necessary. The intervention of adults must be of such subtlety that it remains outside the child's perceptual aspect, and it is up to the parents to be enthusiastic about the discoveries and assimilative revelations that their children are able to make. It is clear that it is not the storytelling that causes development in itself; but, the provocations it awakens and, in an attempt to resolve endogenous conflicts, the individual moves beyond their own limiting reality.

Keywords: Practice telling stories before bed. Egosyntonic . Mother . Phylogenetic inheritance.

INTRODUCTION

Telling stories to children before bed is a practice so old that it is lost in the shadows of time, with no one knowing when it began, which allows us to deduce that it coincides with the origin of articulate speech. This was a situation in which mothers sought to reduce the fear of their young children, a feeling that dominated them and, quite possibly, this psychological action of reassuring their children was aimed at themselves; possibly even more than them.

Human life and existence, in the midst of a world where agriculture and the raising of domestic animals for consumption were not stopped, was an ordeal marked by the constant fear of being without food, given the seasons, climatic phenomena, lack of mechanisms for conserving protein sources of animal origin, which meant that all game had to be consumed in a relatively short time, causing survival situations that, today, are interpreted as barbaric and even go so far as to have individuals let them doubt that measures of such magnitude were ever taken by humans, under any justification.

Society lived under strong tension, whether for fear of the elements of nature, or for fear of attacks by ferocious animals, and there was still the greatest scourge of all, hunger, which attacked silently, refusing to go away, unless unless it was satisfied. And that's where the discussion about children's and women's fear of sleeping begins; because in times of scarcity, the first were those who served as food in order to satisfy the group's hunger. The strategy used was to abandon them in regions of the forest where neighboring tribes carried out their hunts and, therefore, cannibalism was not practiced against a relative or a member of the community itself; but, against a foreigner, which helped to eliminate any guilt, feelings of anger, hatred, wrath or revenge for the victim's relatives. Children were taken to these spaces and abandoned while they slept.

Even though one cannot run the risk of inferring feelings of individuals from other times based on the feelings that were developed and that are considered superior in current cultures, the care of mothers for their children has always been of a very special and, in human prehistory it can be assumed that it was no different, especially because communities were nothing more than collectives, circumspect groups with a very short life expectancy; Therefore, the need to have new members in the family was intense, which made caring for children extreme.

Therefore, we could be making a very serious error of interpretation: if that were the case, why practice cannibalism against those who represented the continuation of the species and against those who were directly responsible for this? And, here, there is an answer that goes far beyond simple rationality and logic; What was at stake was the preservation of the species as a collective and not as an individual. The sacrifice of a few in favor of the survival of others represented a common and understandable act for all, and was even justifiable.

As it was the mothers who provided the most basic care to the children, it was natural for them to maintain a higher level of reliability towards them and an exacerbated level of distrust towards the other members of the collective and, due to the states of abandonment at night, in particular, while sleeping, kidnappings, children started to feel scared when sleepy

and, when they went to sleep, they felt nightmares, waking up scared, screaming, crying and calling for their protectors.

So, at bedtime, children must have started to demand that their mothers be next to them, holding them, which became an inconvenience, because while they were not yet lulled to sleep, how could they get rid of them and, with each attempt, they got closer and squeezed them more intensely. The solution was to look for an alternative that satisfied both mother and child, meeting the child's desires that they were safe and the mothers that they were providing such a feeling to them, and that is when they began to emit high-pitched sounds in low tones, which they improved until they became melodious and, little by little, they realized that they calmed their children.

Throughout the development of thought, mothers had to discover countless ways to adjust the timbre of their voice to a level that would calm their children and induce peaceful sleep, which leads to a much more complex and profound issue, that of that the production of serotonin is linked to the individual's state of security. To do so, he must be calm, peaceful, without fear that something will distress him during his sleep state. In this sense, tension is a state of fear; Therefore, what mothers in the primeval ages had to learn was how to overcome their children's tension at bedtime. But, what was it about this moment that haunted them to the point of feeling unconscious fear, so much so that they were unable to have a restful sleep and, on the contrary, causing imbalance and tension even in a state of semi-consciousness?

Children who do not experience this type of care, in hypothesis, may become anxious and have unfounded fears at bedtime, such as obsessive compulsive disorders, always worried that someone is hiding under the bed and will harm them. kidnapping, during their sleep, which generally makes them wake up scared in the middle of the night, screaming, sweating cold, as if they were running away from a violent animal that could devour them.

In the current situation, with the distance that the population has experienced from Pedagogy and its empirical aspects, these children are referred to the psychologist and then to the psychiatrist who will diagnose them with some syndrome, dousing them with anxiolytic medications, when the solution is, in addition to a strengthened approach to affective-passionate ties with the mother, an elixir to strengthen the child's ego, making him more secure and emotionally balanced.

Not just any story can be told to children at bedtime; these must have a logical sense, a coherence between what one lives and what one intends for the future, allowing, when listening to it, one to be able to fantasize, making it very clear that the fantasy created by human thought is not something , purely, abstract; it is a construction based on what we have as prior

knowledge, making use of freedom of expression, which is linked to each person's cognitive limits.

In this sense, taking what was expressed above as an inflection point, on which we intend to build a thesis, the fear of sleeping that affects children is a phylogenetic inheritance, being stored in their unconscious as a form of natural defense. In the wake of the evolution of the species, superior feelings, such as motherhood and the desire to protect offspring, became ingrained in the spirit of women and they developed ways of guaranteeing the protection of their children, which naturally explains the closeness of their children. With mothers, at least to a greater extent, during childhood and the father remains an ambiguous figure who arouses paradoxical feelings towards himself, in which love and fear towards him are the fundamental bases for the formation of human character.

When associating the practice of reading stories to children at bedtime with high levels of cognition, intelligence and intellectuality, one must be careful not to become a victim of *post hoc thinking*, as a consequence of this, that happened. It cannot be ignored that children who feel secure from an emotional point of view are more likely to achieve success in all their activities, whether individual or collective, because they express themselves better, are more daring, are not suspicious and are also not dominated by insane and paranoid fear ; therefore, the possibility of suffering from anxiety and other psychiatric disorders is much lower when compared, generally, to the global average. There is a causal link between the practice of reading to children at bedtime and high levels of intellectual coefficient; not being able to be tied to literal determinations.

ABOUT THE ACT OF TELLING STORIES TO CHILDREN AT BEDTIME

One of the most ridiculous beliefs that has become an object of absolute value is that the act of reading stories to children at bedtime, devoid of a deeper and more complex meaning, contributes to the formation of their reading capacity. and also increases your future intellectual and cognitive capacity. It is not about the act for the sake of the act; but, of its nuances, interconnected with other endogenous factors, particular and unique to each individual and the social conditions in which they are inserted. The absolute idea that this practice produces miraculous results could not be further out of context, starting with the fact that *Physis 's first concern* is with the survival of the species and, in the specific case of the human being, the psychological condition is one of the most important elements. essential for maintaining the safety of the *species* and not just the individual. This is why, on many occasions, those who

were attacked by attacks of foolishness, being considered crazy, were killed, because their condition of *insanity* caused bad omens among their peers, which put the entire security of society at risk. Those who believe that within the human phenomenological scope, nature is protecting the being based on selfish criteria are very mistaken; all his dictates are altruistic.

In the spectrum of the human condition, man persists in his condition of survival in nature because of his intelligence, which is understood here as the ability to find solutions to problems that, at first glance, appear to be far superior to his meager strengths. A very empathetic belief is that human beings in Antiquity were primitive beasts who lived under the auspices of the stars and gods, superstitious to the point of fearing any phenomenological change such as the expression of divine wrath. This was what allowed knowledge about them and their behavior to reach contemporaries; however, what they kept secret was their extensive knowledge and mastery over deep psychology and its manifestations, especially those people who were surrounded by warlike enemies and who depended on the emotional control of their warriors to participate in intense conflicts and wars.

In this regard, the issue of observing the condition of children with difficulty sleeping at night and even restless sleep, nightmares, could already be the subject of observation and complaints by some mothers to village healers, possibly in search of some elixir, a drug or some strategy that would help solve the problem. And, in this search, they may, at random, have tried to soothe their children with a soft growl and repeating the experience led to the confirmation that its effect was positive.

Here's the question: and before the human species acquired language and gained mastery over it, how did mothers do to lull their children to sleep? This already suggests that behavior is as old as the human being itself and emerged from observing children's behavior over a long period of time. Quite possibly, they produced sounds similar to music and this caused young children to sleep peacefully and have a peaceful sleep.

Another question arises, which at first seems more complex, dealing with the condition that it has to be the mother who carries out this moment or could it be anyone directly linked to the family or the child? The answer to this question, which may seem direct and very transparent, deserves an entire undertaking in understanding that the bond built between mother and child is unique and irreplaceable. Thus, the child does not expect that a substitute for his mother will be able to satisfy his need for protection; She wants her mother's presence, to hear her voice, with the intonation that has already become fixed in her unconscious and that, upon hearing her, a whole aspect of power and happiness opens up in her world and runs into her arms, touching her head on his chest, in order to hear another old acquaintance of his, his

mother's heartbeat and how much it is accelerated by his presence. This is not a simple hug; but, an analysis of how happy she is to see him. This is a very archaic anthropological examination, a phylogenetic inheritance of extreme complexity that is [*almost*] impossible to explain through the traditional paths of positivist thinking that has taken over contemporary human and social sciences.

Still on the emotional bond between mother and child, even if as a baby he cannot express his desire to be and be welcomed by her, that child who did not receive such attention from his mother and was left in the care of third parties, one day, many years later, when she heard the stories of her colleagues, friends and contemporaries about how they were welcomed by their respective mothers, the long hours they spent together and she, sitting on the edge of their bed, before going to sleep, telling them stories fabulous, you will miss having received this type of affection and you will demand the same, there is an emptiness in your life that, even though you are not able to understand the reason and why you feel it, continues to pressure you, which reveals to us that this type of bond is something that refers to a behavior of the species, and cannot be treated as a social construction, because if it were so, it would be enough for the action to cease for its effect to disappear, almost immediately.

At the other end, there is the child, who needs his mother's affection to feel and, at the same time, needs to grow, become an adult, have the power to face his fears and ghosts alone and, it is from and through from the stories his mother tells him that he can accomplish this feat. The realization that he is building his psychological world based on the stories told at night comes when he asks her to repeat the narrative. This demonstrates that he is internalizing the story and the character and, as he asks to repeat it more often, he strengthens the certainty that he is accommodating and assimilating it, in that from then on, he will be the figure represented in the story. play for his own construction which, at this point, is still a mere repetition of what he was told by his mother.

This is the main reason why the stories told cannot be of a warning nature nor have a tragic ending; they must provide an ending in which the hero overcomes challenges, faces adversities, escapes from dangers that are greater than him, hides; but, thinks of a solution and emerges victorious, because when the child assumes, in his mind, the identity of the character in the story, he needs this fantasy of overcoming and victories.

These particular conditions will make him see himself as someone who is strong and fearless, at the same time that he understands that some dangers are too much for him to dare to face, and he must show himself to be smart and intelligent. This makes the child reach the crucial moment of human existence, the Oedipus Complex phase, and cross it safely, because

he sees himself as capable of protecting the object of his love; not needing to take it as an object of neurotic possession, marked by the fear of not being able to keep it and the intrinsic insecurity that can make him an adult with a weakened ego.

This is where we reach the point where we have the conviction to affirm how much the fact of telling stories to children at bedtime contributes to the construction of an egosyntonic self, a strong and powerful self capable of facing life's challenges. and with lower risks of neurosis marks and other personality disorders. Of course, the type of story that is narrated represents the entire *leitmotif* capable of determining this entire condition of personological development , in particular.

What is very transparent is that all of these are situations that are part of the development process of the species and even if, hypothetically, it has undergone some change over a certain moment in its evolution , it proved to be so subtle that the absence of this The type of treatment given to children causes irreparable damage to their lives, even after they become adults. Human beings evolved with a complex brain and now have the ability to abstract; however, some inheritances kept it constant in its specificity and the development of a personality that needed to become complex because of community life made it depend on elements that are unique to it; but, when you have the opportunity to observe the animals, you notice a subtle condition of similarity regarding the expression of sounds at lower levels than normal, as if it were a way of providing tranquility to the puppies.

We are not, under any circumstances, trying to anthropomorphize the care of female animals for their young, much less compare it to the complex act of telling stories to their children by human mothers. It should be noted that the silence of adults is something that greatly frightens children and, when mothers sit at the head of the bed to tell stories, this gives them more than just satisfaction; It's like a feeling of relief from a tension that you can't explain where it comes from and how it arises.

ABOUT THE PROCESS OF ASSIMILATION AND ACCOMMODATION OF STORIES TOLD AT BEDTIME BY CHILDREN

Assimilation and accommodation are processes that are part of the formation of the individual cognitive personological structure , and what we intend to clarify is how they happen in children's thoughts based on the stories that are told to them, specifically at bedtime. It must be considered that this action begins to be practiced by mothers when their children are still

newborn babies; therefore, an entire understanding of how children act must be considered and interpreted.

Assimilation is the cognitive process by which an individual integrates (classifies) new perceptual, motor or conceptual data into previous cognitive structures (WADSWORTH, 1996), that is, when the child has new experiences (seeing, hearing or experiencing new situations) seeks, in some way, using the cognitive and intellectual tools at their disposal, to adapt these new stimuli to the thought structures they already have and believe they have mastered. In the case of a small child, who is not yet able to articulate speech, the interest and deduction are in the aspect of the voice timbre applied by the mother when narrating the story and, in a short time, he will be sleeping a very comforting sleep, not only because of his inability to assimilate what is said, considering that he does not understand what is expressed, because his brain has not developed the linguistic structures capable of interpreting words. There is also the condition of requiring more time in a state of sleep. Jean Piaget defines assimilation as “an integration with previous structures, which may remain invariable or are more or less modified by this integration itself, but without discontinuity with the previous state, that is, without being destroyed, but simply accommodating to the new situation” (PIAGET, 1996, p. 13).

For the child to be able to carry out assimilation is a highly complex task, because their thinking, their cognitive and intellectual condition and their vocabulary dimension, the number of words in their memory and more, the ability to correlate a vocabulary term to the corresponding element is very reduced when compared to that of adults, especially because of the experience they do not yet have, especially if they are raised in a restricted environment of freedom and broader contact with the world. As he develops his cognitive potential, he expands the entire process of intellectual construction, which is still very far from assimilation. Just note that, first, he begins to identify the central characters of the story and asks what they represent; for example, when the mother says that *there was a kingdom*, she questions 'what is a kingdom?' In the same proportion, when it is said that there was a princess, the child repeats the question, directing his curiosity to the highlighted object and so on until he can build a chain of image representations in his memory, through which he can carry out the process of assimilation when you hear the story again.

This process is slow and complex, requiring parents to let the child elaborate his or her own epistemic construction, and it is up to them to assist the child when he or she seeks help, which may not occur as often as the parental anxiety desires and, thus, What they can do is create and/or provoke learning situations through images and stories that arouse curiosity in relation to the object, fact, or situation suggested.

This aspect being reported is related to a pedagogical issue of epistemological development and the telling of stories for children at bedtime cannot be dominated by this entire set of pedagogical ideals, even though it is known that the entire set of words heard and their expressions, as well as the assimilations carried out will remain and will reappear, through reminiscent memory, at some point in their future lives. What is important to clarify here is that this entire process must be carried out by the child, in their own way, without adult interference, making them believe that everything was created and recreated based on their own cognition, through their autonomous construction action. of his intellectuality.

The story told by the mother to the child at bedtime should have no other interest than to make the child sleep peacefully, feeling safe and welcomed. Everything else that goes beyond this must be of the child's particular and autonomous interest, and it is up to him to make the assimilations in the way he sees fit, including seeking help when he deems it necessary. The intervention of adults must be of such subtlety that it remains outside the child's perceptual aspect, and it is up to the parents to be enthusiastic about the discoveries and assimilative revelations that their children are able to make.

In this aspect, we already go beyond the field of phylogenetic inheritance to enter the scope of ontogenetic inheritance, a condition that, it is observed, is constructed and structured by the individual himself, even if the child does not yet have the slightest notion of what he is working on. your *intrapsychic* world. When we reach this point of understanding human cognitive development, we have a perception of how much the practice of telling stories to children at bedtime can contribute to their cognitive and intellectual development and maturation, from the moment they reaches the stage of abstraction and complex logical-deductive thinking.

It may seem strange to the reader when they come across this part of the text, where elsewhere it is stated that this practice has nothing to do with children's cognitive development; but, it is observed that this cannot be the *declared intention* of the parents, since this is an *undeclared intention* of the children and what's more, the impact will happen many years later and later, throughout their entire lives. In those first moments of life, the child's entire interest is in feeling close to someone they trust and feeling protected during their sleeping hours, when they are completely defenseless and unable to ask for help.

In the same proportion and time in which assimilation occurs, including the timbre of the mother's voice, this is an important element to be considered, because it is based on their determination and mnemonic fixation that the child will know when the mother is well or not, emotionally. ; practice that lasts throughout individual existence. Piaget (1975) defines the

cognitive operation of accommodation (by analogy with biological *accommodations*) as any modification of assimilation schemes under the influence of external situations (environment) to which they apply.

Accommodation represents a conflict situation for the individual, in the most specific case that this work deals with, the child, which will happen when they are unable to assimilate a new stimulus, that is, there is no cognitive structure that is capable of assimilating the new information depending on the particularities of this new stimulus (NITZKE et al ., 1997a), which may be simple ignorance or the absence of experiences, which does not generate mnemonic situations with which any comparative link can be created. Faced with this impasse, there are only two solutions left: create a new scheme or modify an existing scheme. Both actions result in a change in cognitive structure. Once accommodation has occurred, the child can try to assimilate the stimulus again, and once the cognitive structure has been modified, the stimulus is readily assimilated.

It turns out that the child does not have the brain conditions to carry out such actions in thought and the result is that he seeks help from an adult so that he can build his cognitive structure, a situation that remains stable until around six years of age, when it begins to change some words, creating different ways of expressing themselves, what Piaget (1896-1980) called *linguistic autonomy* , a moment in which parents complain that the child until that moment expressed himself so correctly and now is saying *everything wrong*, referring to the expression of some words.

When mothers tell stories to their children at bedtime and, ideally, the story is told and not read, because this demonstrates greater autonomy and greater power, the advent of accommodation is what is most expressed, because almost everything there will be new for the child and, at the beginning, the characters will be the assimilative representation of the parents, for example, the princess or the queen will be image representations of the mother, the king and the prince in love will be image representations of the father, until the child reaches condition of assimilating both one character and another to himself, at which point he begins to process his identity in an abstract way, assuming logic as an instrument for developing his thinking.

The action that begins as a simple object of security and balance for children's sleep gradually shows its relevance in the construction of logical thinking, allowing those children who experience such an attitude on the part of their mothers to become more capable of getting involved. in the logical world, processing complex thoughts with greater potential and thus becoming more expressive in terms of creativity, which is nothing more than the expansive determination of the condition of abstract intelligence. Nothing proves that this child will be a

great reader or a writer as an adult; This is already a type of speculation that is beyond anyone's control. What has been presented so far is the possibility that children who have had the privilege of having their mothers tell them stories at bedtime have a greater load of words and terms in their memory, which encourages greater action towards assimilation and accommodation, generating situations of cognitive conflicts in which the search for a solution, by the child himself, favors his cognitive and intellectual development. In this sense, it is not the storytelling that causes development in itself; but, the provocations it awakens and, in an attempt to resolve endogenous conflicts, the individual moves beyond their own limiting reality.

CONCLUSION

What we sought to discuss in this work was the anthropological meaning of the practice of reading stories to children before bed, a very common situation among the human species and which, over time, especially with the hyper modernization of life, comes ceasing to be something commonplace in families. Analyzes and interpretations demonstrate that its practice contributes to the balanced formation of a strengthened and healthy ego in the child, making them capable of being an adult less prone to neuroses and other psychological dysfunctions.

In recent times there has been a distancing from the role of motherhood and what has been observed is a reduction in the number of adults reporting that their mothers or others responsible for their care told them stories at bedtime. In a survey carried out by Souza (2023), with teenagers aged between 15 and 18 years old, the scientist was able to verify that 9.4% of those interviewed responded that this practice was *constant* in their homes when they were young; 20.4% responded that this *sometimes* happened in their homes ; 12.65% reported that such an event was *rarely* adopted by their parents and 57.55% responded that such an event had *never* happened in their homes, by anyone.

This loss of the affective relationship produced by the absence of the practice of telling stories to children by mothers ends up creating a generation of anxious and suspicious, frightened individuals with cognitive and intellectual potential that will take longer to manifest in existence, considering that communication of terms, images, descriptions of places and situations end up compromised and equidistant from the developmental condition human. It must be clarified that nature did not create any substitute for the mother, whether biological or mechanical; certain functions, which seem simple and which are supposed to be possible for anyone to do, must be performed exclusively by them. When a child refuses to let others replace his mother in this task of telling him bedtime stories, it is not because of custom or emotional

ties; It is an archaic, natural mechanism that is a very strong, deep and complex biological inheritance.

Abram Kardiner and Edward Preble (1964) report that children, studied by them, in the Marquesas Islands and who are raised without due attention from their mothers are suspicious, suspicious, always looking everywhere, without fixing their eyes on their interlocutors. . It is noteworthy that on these islands, female infanticide is still practiced, as a way of controlling the population rate and mitigating the effects of periods of food scarcity in the region. The girls, already in their teens, are abandoned in regions of the forest where neighboring tribes carry out their hunts, and the same does the other tribes that inhabit the islands.

The narration of stories to children at bedtime, by mothers, will contribute to their epistemic, cognitive and intellectual development as they begin to resolve their conflicts produced by accommodation, an inevitable situation given the limited extent of their knowledge and which , little by little he becomes organized as he experiences knowledge situations, enriching his mnemonic scope.

The practice that, at the beginning of a child's life, represents a phylogenetic aspect, because it is a behavior created by mothers in remote times and that has been repeated in a very natural way and, what attracts attention is that the condition of conflicts generated by acquisition of new words and assimilation and accommodation of words, representation of images and characters is being internalized in order to be part of the human ontogenetic process, which directly influences the construction and consolidation of intelligence.

When it comes to building personality, nothing will replace the mother's presence for the child at bedtime, especially telling him fantastic stories, in which a character goes through incredible adventures and overcomes them all, becoming stronger and braver every day. At first, it is his mother's voice that welcomes him and calms him, allowing him a peaceful and restful sleep; later, when his personological development process begins to structure his Ego, he transfers the *protective maternal figure* to a symbolic representation of refuge and with the power to transform him into an adult, through his speech and his stories, which the child becomes internalized and, through the attempt to resolve the conflicts produced by accommodation, creates a broader and more complex intrinsic world.

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